

**BIORemediation systems exploiting SYnergies
for improved removal of Mixed pOllutants**

Deliverable D7.2

Communication tools (poster, leaflet, roll-up, brochure)

Deliverable information

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Project Profile

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Executive Summary

This deliverable summarises the communication tools designed under the BIOSYSMO project. In particular, the project poster, project poster template, roll-up, leaflet and brochure are presented herein. In this document, some preliminary guidelines are given for the communication strategy, which will be described in detail in Deliverable 7.3, including the Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of the Results. The need to promote the project in different media is essential and it is highlighted why. The key messages and target audiences must be identified when sharing the communication material, while also guidelines for the project acknowledgment are provided. All communication material, as well as the upcoming dissemination tools, are included in the project's website as well as in the internal SharePoint site that the consortium uses to enhance collaboration.

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EXE	EXELISIS
NGOs	Non-governmental organizations
PEDR	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results

1 Communication activities

1.1 Why communication?

Communication aims to make the project known to its community providing clear and easy-to-understand messages to the relevant stakeholders. Communication starts from the beginning of the project, in contrast with dissemination which kicks off right after the first results are delivered.

For this reason, a detailed communication plan is built, identifying target audiences, defining clear objectives and setting out a time plan for upcoming activities¹. Communication activities request the cooperation of the whole consortium to highlight the expected impacts of the research developments, the challenges a project faces and the expected outcomes. The BIOSYSMO communication strategy is going to be presented in detail and continuously updated under Deliverables 7.3, 7.4 and 7.5 Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR).

Printed materials designed for communication purposes aim to showcase the project's main concept and objectives during conferences, workshops and events the consortium organises or participates in. All materials comply with the project's visual identity, colour guidelines and the overall project identity.

1.2 Target audiences and key messages

The European Commission (EC) has specified detailed target audiences to address several communication activities. Those audiences are summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Targeted communication audiences

¹https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communicatio_en.htm

Moreover, the BIOSYSMO consortium is aiming to mainly address key messages to:

- **Industry and specific end-user communities**, including a) environmental consulting and engineering companies and polluting industries, as well as b) plant breeders, plant producers and microbial inoculant producers. Information on improved effectiveness and economic feasibility of water, soil and sediment treatment techniques are going to be shared, accompanied by aspects related to mixture toxicity and risk assessment. New plant and microbial resources and the benefits of the newly developed and tested methodologies for the design and construction of biosystems are going to also be promoted.
- **Research communities, and EU institutions** specialising in water, soil and sediment bioremediation, as well as systems and computational biology.
- **Policymakers, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and authorities**, focusing on the environmental, economic and social benefits of the developments, new regulations and safety-related aspects.
- **Citizens** interested in environmental protection and novel bioremediation techniques, allowing a safer and cleaner EU environment, promoting citizens' health and leading to greener cities.

1.3 Communication responsibilities

Communication of project results requires teamwork and to this end, all members of the consortium are bound to communicate the project concept and impacts, under the lead of the Dissemination Manager of BIOSYSMO, EXELISIS (EXE). EXE will guide the consortium to follow the suggested guidelines leading to successful communication and provide any support for improving the communication material and promoting the project to the specified audiences.

1.4 Project acknowledgement in communication

The consortium will follow the EC guidelines and acknowledge the EC funding in all communication and dissemination materials. All partners are informed to include the following acknowledgement and disclaimer in all relevant files shared for different purposes, as well as including the European Union flag (Figure 2).

“The project BIOSYSMO has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101060211.”

“Funded by the European Union under GA no 101060211. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Funded by the
European Union

Funded by the
European Union

Figure 2. European Union flag in different layouts

1.5 Communication materials SharePoint

All Dissemination and Communication (D&C) materials will be included (and updated as necessary) in high quality on the BIOSYSMO website and the consortium internal SharePoint repository, aiming to be easily accessible to the consortium at any time.

2 Communication tools

The communication tools developed under BIOSYSMO include the project poster, project poster template, roll-up, leaflet, and brochure. The following sections describe in detail the design and content of the material.

2.1 BIOSYSMO poster

2.1.1 Official poster

The official BIOSYSMO poster (Figure 3) was designed to match the BIOSYSMO identity, aiming to be used in different events to promote the project, and includes:

- Title and logo of the project
- Short abstract
- Project objectives
- BIOSYSMO procedures
- Impacts and
- Applications
- Project consortium
- Project details

Figure 3. BIOSYSMO official poster

2.1.2 Poster template

The poster template (Figure 4) was designed in a PowerPoint format (.pptx) in order to support and facilitate the consortium researchers to include their results in a uniform template when presenting their advancements of work in dedicated conferences, summits, or exhibitions.

Figure 4. BIOSYSMO poster template

2.2 BIOSYSMO leaflet

The BIOSYSMO leaflet (Figure 5) is an A5 format flyer that describes very briefly the project and focuses on its applications while it also provides the project details and links to the BIOSYSMO website and social media. The information is presented therefore in a concise way and the one-page format makes it an ideal tool to be used for different dissemination purposes.

Figure 5. BIOSYSMO leaflet

2.3 BIOSYSMO roll-up

The project roll-up (Figure 6) is designed to be used in several events and highlights the main tagline, key information of the project as well as the project consortium and the project website and social media platforms.

The main image used for the roll-up focuses on microorganisms, which are the core of the project and they assist in the bioremediation and phytoremediation of soils, waters, and sediments. The roll-up also follows the identity and colour guidelines and includes the project representatives and for this reason, it is a tool to be used by all of the partners in exhibitions, fairs, conferences etc.

Figure 6. BIOSYSMO roll-up

2.4 BIOSYSMO brochure

The official brochure is an A4 threefold, which is an ideal form in order to include all the necessary information related to the project. The brochure can be distributed during scientific conferences as well as in other dissemination activities, as it both includes general but also more detailed information about the project.

The brochure includes in brief all the important information of the project:

- Title and logo of the project
- Project details
- Coordinator and the team, including a map
- Applications
- Brief description of the project
- Procedure
- Objectives
- Impacts
- Website and social media

Figure 7. BIOSYSMO brochure

3 Conclusions

Communication tools play a vital role in the promotion of a project and its activities. This deliverable D7.2 includes the communication tools developed under the BIOSYSMO project and include the project poster, project poster template, roll-up, leaflet and brochure. These tools are going to be used by the consortium and beyond to communicate and, at a later stage disseminate, the project results and maximise its impact. This material is developed early on at the beginning of the project, while updates and newer versions might be needed during the project implementation. These developments, as well as the initial designs, are going to be included in Deliverable 7.3.

Annex I: BIOSYSMO posters

Official poster

BIOSYSMO

BIOremediation systems exploiting SYnergieS for improved reMoval of mixed pOLLutants

ABSTRACT

BIOSYSMO develops a computationally assisted framework for designing and optimizing synergistic biosystems (bacteria, fungi, and plants) for efficient degradation and sequestration of pollutants in soil, sediments, and water. The project screens samples from polluted sites to identify existing microorganisms to metabolize target pollutants. Research is expanded to microorganisms by applying data mining tools to genomic and metagenomic data to identify improvements in biosystems.

OBJECTIVES

- Bioremediate polluted soil, water and sediments
- Collect and characterize polluted samples
- Design, apply and optimize synergistic biosystems
- Enhance plant-microbe interactions and engineered bacteria
- Maximize pollutants uptake and degradation

PROCEDURE

IMPACTS

- 9 Target Contaminated Sites
- 5 Bioremediation Strategies
- 70-80% Pollutants Removal
- TRL4-5 BIOSYSMO Technologies
- Biobased solutions for zero-pollution
- Circular bio-based systems to reverse climate change
- New improved synergistic biosystems
- Lab (TRL4) and field validated (TRL5) bioremediation
- Reduced environmental footprints of bioremediation
- Healthy symbiotic microbes-plants biosystems
- Protected soil health and water quality
- Restored biodiversity

APPLICATIONS

1. Water phytoremediation
2. Groundwater remediation
3. Soil phytoremediation
4. Soil bioaugmentation
5. Sediment bioremediation

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Poster template

PLACE EVENT LOGO HERE

TITLE

AUTHORS:

PLACE
INSTITUTION
LOGO HERE

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Annex II: BIOSYSMO leaflet

**BIOREMEDIATION SYSTEMS EXPLOITING SYNERGIES
FOR IMPROVED REMOVAL OF MIXED POLLUTANTS**

- WATER PHYTOREMEDIATION
- GROUNDWATER REMEDIATION
- SOIL PHYTOREMEDIATION
- SOIL BIOAUGMENTATION
- SEDIMENT BIOREMEDIATION

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PROJECT PARTNERS

Annex III: BIOSYSMO roll-up

BIOSYSMO

BIOREMEDIATION SYSTEMS EXPLOITING SYNERGIES FOR IMPROVED REMOVAL OF MIXED POLLUTANTS

13 ORGANISATIONS

8 COUNTRIES

9 FIELD SITES

EU CONTRIBUTION 4.8M

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Annex IV: BIOSYSMO brochure

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#BIOSYSMO

BIOREMEDIATION SYSTEMS EXPLOITING SYNERGIES FOR IMPROVED REMOVAL OF MIXED POLLUTANTS

PROJECT DETAILS
START DATE: SEPTEMBER 1, 2022
DURATION: 4 YEARS
EU CONTRIBUTION: EUR 4.8M

WWW.BIOSYSMO.EU

13 ORGANISATIONS

8 COUNTRIES

9 FIELD SITES

EU CONTRIBUTION 4.8M

APPLICATIONS

1. **Water phytoremediation:** Polluted water treated with plant/microbe hydroponic systems and enhanced with bioelectrochemical systems (BES).
2. **Groundwater remediation:** Microstructured electroactive microbial biofilms applied in BES reactors to process contaminated water: treatment of pollutants at electrodes and at water volume.
3. **Soil phytoremediation:** Modified poplar lines to integrate new traits from microorganisms and plants for endophyte root colonization and pollutants resistance.
4. **Soil bioaugmentation:** Genetically improved strains with high contaminant removal are applied to bioaugment the community, to test biostimulation and to adjust soil physicochemical factors.
5. **Sediment bioremediation:** Uptake and biodegradation of contaminants enhanced by microorganisms inoculated in plant-sediment systems in estuarine environments.

IMPACTS

- 9 Target Contaminated Sites
- 5 Bioremediation Strategies
- 70-80% Pollutants Removal
- TRL4-5 BIOSYSMO Technologies

PROCEDURE

IN BRIEF

BIOSYSMO develops a computationally assisted framework for designing and optimizing synergistic biosystems (bacteria, fungi, and plants) for efficient degradation and sequestration of pollutants in soil, sediments, and water. The project screens samples from polluted sites to identify existing microorganisms to metabolize target pollutants. Research is expanded to microorganisms by applying data mining tools to genomic and metagenomic data to identify improvements in biosystems.

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